

A small family unit of house mouse (*Mus musculus*) with anomalous colouration in Slovakia

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Abstract: In this paper, a small family unit (i.e., deme) of the house mouse (*Mus musculus*) from south-eastern Slovakia is presented, where thirteen individuals exhibited anomalous colouration with signs of flavism. The mice were trapped over seven days (14–20.1.2025) during the winter season in the garage of a family house in the countryside. In total, 23 individuals were obtained (12 males, 11 females). Morphological determination and subsequent dissection confirmed that the trapped mice belonged to three age classes: 8 adults, 2 subadults, and 13 juveniles. The dorsal fur for thirteen mice was yellow (or beige), with slightly darker fur along the middle of the back; the auricles, feet, and tail were light yellow; and the colouration on the belly ranged from light to white. These findings are important not only in terms of colour anomalies but also in terms of genetics.

Keywords: deme, flavism, Muridae, pigment mutation, rodents

Introduction

The house mouse (*Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758) is one of the most common and widespread representatives of the family Muridae worldwide (Macholán, 1996a, b). Several populations exhibit commensal (synanthropic) living habits associated with human dwellings, farms, food stores, and other anthropogenic habitats. Other populations live part or all the year in the wild, with varying habitat selection (Pelikán, 1974; Zejda, 1975) and are referred to as eusynanthropic. Studies by Pelikán (1974) and Zejda (1975) have documented that although house mice migrate to fields in the summer, they later move back to human settlements. Pocock et al. (2004, 2005) showed that house mice living in commensal habitats can rapidly adapt to new conditions shaped by specific aspects of human lifestyles, which are constantly changing. Therefore, mice must respond quickly to these rapid changes by adapting to new foods and using whatever is available as shelter (Witmer & Jojola, 2006). Moreover, indoor living house mice tend to live in localised populations with high densities and low dispersal rates, in small family units called “demes” (Latham & Mason, 2004), and exhibit

typical territorial behaviour (Pocock et al., 2005; Frynta et al., 2005).

According to several authors (Binkley, 2001; Imes et al., 2006; Whitman, 2009; Łopucki & Mróz, 2010; McCardle, 2012; Steen & Sonerud, 2012; Łopucki et al., 2013; Nedyalkov et al., 2014; Čanády et al., 2008a; Čanády, 2015, 2016), colouration in mammals is most often influenced by the presence or absence of melanin pigment in the cortex and medulla of hair, in the epidermis of the skin, and in the iris of the eyes. Tim Caro (2005) showed that most mammals exhibit gradual variation in colouration across populations, while some populations show discontinuous variation and are either white or black. The studies mentioned above confirmed that the most common abnormality in mammals is albinism, the less common is melanism, and the least common is flavism.

According to the above-mentioned studies, the albinotic phenotype exhibits a range of distinct characteristics. Albinism can be classified into different types. The first is complete (true) albinism, which is marked by an overall lighter or even white coat, pink skin, and red eyes. The second type is leucism, caused by a reduction or absence of pigment in the fur, while

the colour of the eyes and skin remains unaffected. The third type is piebaldism, or white spotting (also known as partial albinism), which results from pigment loss in specific body regions, manifesting as patches, bands on the coat, or white tips on the ears or tail. This form of albinism involves a significant portion of the animal's body. Partial albinos are relatively common and typically lack the pink eyes characteristic of complete albinos (Hiler 1983).

Melanism is a genetic phenomenon characterised by an increased production of the dark pigment melanin, resulting in a darker or black colouration of the skin, fur, or feathers in animals compared to the typical colouring of their species (Caro, 2005; Roulin, 2014). This trait arises from mutations in genes responsible for the synthesis and distribution of melanin, such as the *MC1R* gene (Kerns et al., 2004; Hoekstra, 2006). Melanism can play an important role in ecological and evolutionary processes, including camouflage, thermoregulation, and social communication among individuals (Hoekstra, 2006; Nachman et al., 2003).

Flavism in mammals is a rare pigmentation anomaly characterised by an overall yellowish or pale coat colouration due to a shift in melanin synthesis, favouring pheomelanin (yellow to red pigment) over eumelanin (black or brown pigment), without a complete loss of melanin as seen in albinism. It results from genetic alterations in key pigmentation genes such as *ASIP* (Agouti signalling protein) or *MC1R* (Melanocortin 1 receptor), which regulate melanin type-switching in melanocytes. Affected individuals usually retain normal eye pigmentation, distinguishing flavism from albinism. This condition has been documented in various small mammals and is considered a form of hereditary colour polymorphism (Millar et al., 1995; Barsh, 1996; Våge et al., 1997; Hoekstra, 2006; Łopucki & Mróz, 2010; and others)

These anomalies in colouration have been noted in several mammalian groups, such as insectivores, bats, rodents, carnivores, ungulates, primates, and others. For rodents of various genera (e.g., *Microtus*, *Myodes* [*Clethrionomys*], *Apodemus*, *Mus*), colour anomalies are common (Binkley, 2001; Łopucki & Mróz, 2010; McCardle, 2012; Steen & Sonnerud, 2012; Łopucki et al., 2013; Čanády et al., 2008a; Čanády, 2015, 2016; Csanády, 2022).

Flavism in the Czech and Slovak Republics (formerly Czechoslovakia) has been documented in

Apodemus flavicollis by Hanák (1957), in *A. sylvaticus* by Štusák (1987), and in *A. agrarius* by Čanády (2016). Flavism has also been recorded in *Myodes (C.) glareolus* (Literák & Zejda, 1995), in the house mouse, *Mus musculus* (Hanák, 1957), and in the steppe mouse, *M. spicilegus* (Čanády et al., 2008a; Csanády, 2022).

The present study describes thirteen individuals of *Mus musculus* exhibiting signs of abnormal colouration, specifically flavism. These data contribute to the overall knowledge of anomalous colouration in this species.

Material and methods

During a short period of seven days (14–20.1.2025), the presence of house mice was recorded in the village of Trstené pri Hornáde (south-eastern Slovakia), in a garage where sunflowers were stored for winter bird feeding. A biological trapping method using Chmela-type live traps (175 trap-nights in total) was employed to capture this small family unit. The traps were baited with nuts or sunflower seeds and exposed for seven days, with checks conducted several times throughout the day.

Data on reproductive aspects were obtained from 23 mice (11 females and 12 males). The age, sex, and reproductive status of the trapped mice were determined through dissection based on the condition of their genitals. Male reproductive activity was evaluated by the descent of the testes from the abdominal cavity into the scrotum, the size and volume of the testes, and the size of the vesicular glands (Table 1).

According to Pelikán (1974) and Csanády et al. (2021), the animals were divided into three age categories: adults (females with visible placental scars, swollen uterus, and either pregnant or lactating, i.e., with functioning mammary glands; males with scrotal testes and a fully developed cauda epididymis), subadults (females with inactive reproductive organs, small nipples, and a closed vagina; males with developed abdominal testes), and juveniles (females with a threadlike vagina and undeveloped uterus; males with barely visible testes).

The following parameters were measured in each mouse (see Table 1): body mass (excluding the weight of embryos in pregnant females, W) with an accuracy of 0.01 g, and four linear variables (measured by

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Table 1. A small family unit (deme) of house mice (*Mus musculus*) with natural and anomalous colouration (i.e., flavistic colour), caught from 14–20.1.2025 in the village of Trstené pri Hornáde (south-eastern Slovakia).

No.	sex	age	W	HBL	TL	HFL	EL	colour	Reproduction notes
552	female	adult	15.5	86.5	61.0	15.0	13.0	flavistic	multiparous, gravid (E: 2 right+3 left), 0.5g, 0.5 mm
565	female	adult	18.0	90.0	69.5	15.0	13.0	natural	primigravid, gravid (E: 3 right + 4 left), 6.0g, 16 mm
568	female	adult	19.0	85.0	65.0	15.0	14.0	natural	primiparous
554	male	adult	16.5	82.0	65.0	15.0	13.5	flavistic	TeL (7.0 mm), TeW (5.0 mm), VeL (8.0 mm): full sex. active.
564	male	adult	15.0	81.0	63.0	15.0	14.0	natural	TeL (7.0 mm), TeW (3.5 mm), VeL (9.0 mm): full sex. active.
566	male	adult	17.0	82.0	63.0	15.0	13.0	natural	TeL (6.0 mm), TeW (3.5 mm), VeL (5.0 mm): non-full sex. active.
567	male	adult	16.0	81.0	63.5	15.0	13.0	natural	TeL (6.0 mm), TeW (3.5 mm), VeL (-): non-full sex. active.
569	male	adult	15.0	80.0	66.0	15.5	14.0	natural	TeL (6.5 mm), TeW (4.0 mm), VeL (3.0 mm): non-full sex. active.
553	female	subadult	13.5	76.0	59.0	15.0	14.0	flavistic	
555	female	subadult	12.5	74.0	57.0	15.0	13.0	flavistic	
558	female	juvenile	5.0	52.0	39.0	14.0	12.0	flavistic	
560	female	juvenile	8.5	67.0	52.0	15.0	13.5	flavistic	
570	female	juvenile	7.5	69.0	53.0	15.0	13.0	natural	
571	female	juvenile	7.0	65.0	53.0	15.0	14.0	natural	
572	female	juvenile	8.0	69.0	57.0	15.0	12.0	natural	
574	female	juvenile	7.0	61.0	51.0	14.5	13.0	flavistic	
573	male	juvenile	7.0	66.0	57.0	15.0	12.0	natural	
559	male	juvenile	5.0	57.0	39.0	14.0	12.	flavistic	
560	male	juvenile	6.0	59.0	42.0	14.5	12.0	flavistic	
561	male	juvenile	6.0	62.0	44.0	15.0	13.0	flavistic	
562	male	juvenile	4.5	55.0	41.0	13.5	12.0	flavistic	
563	male	juvenile	4.5	57.5	40.5	14.0	12.0	flavistic	
557	male	juvenile	4.5	55.0	36.0	14.0	11.0	flavistic	

Legends: head-and-body length (HBL), tail length (TL), hind-foot length (HFL), ear length (EL), testicular length (TeL), testicular width (TeW), and seminal vesicle length (VeL).

using a Vernier calliper), including head-and-body length (HBL), tail length (TL), hind-foot length (HFL), and ear length (EL). In mature males, reproductive organs were measured: testicular length (TeL), testicular width (TeW), and seminal vesicle length (VeL). Males with a seminal vesicle length

greater than 6.0 mm were considered to have full sexual activity, while those with a seminal vesicle length of less than 6.0 mm were considered to have reduced sexual activity. In pregnant females, the number of embryos was counted separately for each uterine horn (Csanády et al., 2021).

Mature females were also divided into four groups based on the type of parity, as described by Balčiauskienė et al. (2015) and Balčiauskienė & Balčiauskas (2016): nulliparous (females with no visible breeding signs), primigravid (females with the first litter, regardless of the embryos' age), primiparous (females with one litter, visible placental scars present from only one litter), and multiparous (females with two litters, placental scars from the first litter and embryos from the second, or placental scars from two litters). In this study, three groups were recorded (excluding nulliparous females; see Table 1).

All flavistic mice were preserved in 96% benzyl alcohol and were deposited in the collections of the East Slovak Museum in Košice.

Results and discussion

The house mouse belongs to the group of mice characterised by light grey-brown, ochre-brown, or dark-grey to dark colouration on the back. The colour of the abdomen is highly variable, ranging from snow-white to yellowish to almost grey in subadults and juveniles (Macholán, 1996a, b). The same natural colouration was also observed in the Slovak population (Csanády et al., 2021). Morphological examination and subsequent dissection revealed that the captured mice belonged to three distinct age categories: 8 adults, 2 subadults, and 13 juveniles. Notably, all 13 anomalously coloured individuals exhibited traits consistent with flavism, thereby meeting the diagnostic criteria for this pigmentation anomaly. The dorsal fur was yellow (or beige), with slightly darker fur in the middle of the back; the auricles, feet, and tail were light yellow, and the colouration on the belly ranged from light to white. On the contrary, the eyes did not show any deviation from the normal colouring and were darkly pigmented (Fig. 1). Moreover, there were no significant differences in body size compared to the normally coloured individuals from the Slovak population (Čanády et al., 2008b; Csanády et al., 2021). It should be emphasised at this point that the capture of the mentioned individuals took place directly in a rural environment (a house garage), where no poultry or other livestock are kept. However, during the winter months, sunflower seeds are stored there for supplementary feeding of birds,

which likely explains the survival of the individuals in this environment.

Moreover, rabbits and poultry are kept year-round in the neighbouring house, making it highly probable that the individuals may have originated from there and subsequently colonised the mentioned garage. It should also be noted that no one in the immediate vicinity is known to keep snakes, either for breeding or feeding purposes, which rules out the possibility of escaped individuals. The fact that the village of Trstené pri Hornáde is in south-eastern Slovakia (Košická kotlina basin), a region where the presence of a related species, the mound-building mouse *Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882, has long been confirmed (e.g., Čanády et al., 2009; Csanády et al., 2019, 2020; Csanády, 2025 and others) – and in which individuals with the same colour anomaly have also been recorded (cf. Čanády et al., 2008; Csanády, 2022) – could raise doubts about the correctness of the identification. However, the author's extensive experience with the research of *M. spicilegus* rules out such a misidentification. Moreover, this species does not inhabit human dwellings and does not breed during the winter season.

Based on the captures obtained, it is likely that there were two distinct family groups. The first consisted of an adult male (554), an adult female (552), and their offspring – all displaying flavistic colouring. The second group comprised individuals with typical (normal) pigmentation. The distribution of colour morphs across different age classes suggests separate reproductive histories, which likely correspond to independently breeding adult individuals.

When comparing the relationship between head-and-body length and body weight in juvenile individuals (Fig. 2), it was found that flavistic individuals exhibited smaller body dimensions compared to normally coloured ones. Despite the small sample size, these results suggest that the fitness of flavistic individuals may be lower than that of normally coloured individuals.

Coat colour in *M. musculus* is often genetically inherited, and flavism may result from recessive mutations in pigmentation genes, such as *Tyr*. If colour inheritance follows Mendelian patterns and is recessive, then a high proportion of uniformly coloured offspring indicates limited genetic mixing – that is, breeding within the same colour morph – which was certainly the case here.

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Fig. 1a. Flavistic house mice (*Mus musculus*) captured January 14–20, 2025, in Trstené pri Hornáde (SE Slovakia); dorsal and ventral views. (Photo: A. Csanády).

Fig. 1b [left], c [right]. Flavistic colour variants of house mice (*Mus musculus*) captured on January 14–20, 2025, in Trstené pri Hornáde (SE Slovakia); dorsal and ventral views. (Photo: A. Csanády).

Fig. 1d [left], e [right]. Flavistic colour variants of house mice (*Mus musculus*) captured between January 14–20, 2025, in Trstené pri Hornáde (SE Slovakia); dorsal and ventral views. Note: Top row, left is naturally coloured *Mus musculus* (Sokol'any, December 2024), shown for comparison with the colour mutation. (Photos: P. Krišovský, A. Csanády).

The presence of flavistic individuals in *Mus musculus* from eastern Slovakia suggests that mutations affecting the *Tyr* gene, which plays a central role in melanin synthesis, are persistently maintained within this population. This observation is consistent with previous findings on the genetic basis of pigment variation and mutations in melanin-related genes (e.g., Barsh, 2001; Oetting & King, 2003; Błaszczuk et al., 2005). These results support the hypothesis that such genetic information is stably maintained within the population over time. According to several authors (Binkley, 2001; Imes et

al., 2006; Łopucki & Mróz, 2010), recessive alleles affecting colour anomalies can persist in the population for a long time and, under certain conditions, may also be phenotypically expressed (Silvers, 1979).

In Poland, most cases of anomalous colouration in rodents have been recorded in habitats exhibiting varying degrees of isolation, which typically result from suboptimal or unfavourable environmental conditions (Łopucki & Mróz, 2010). This pattern supports the hypothesis that environmental stressors (isolation) may influence the expression and

Fig. 2. Relationship between body weight (g) and head-and-body length in naturally coloured (triangles) and flavistic (squares) juvenile *Mus musculus*.

persistence of recessive alleles in populations of ground-dwelling small mammals.

An interesting case was reported by Brown (1965), who discovered a population of house mice on a farm in Missouri carrying a recessive mutation (*p*) that causes pink eyes and pale-yellow fur. A live-trapping study conducted over 1.5 years in and around a granary revealed that, in December 1962, 30.3% of the population exhibited this mutant phenotype. After domestic cats were introduced, selective predation rapidly eliminated the pale-yellow mice, and by April 1963 none remained. The normally pigmented agouti mice survived due to their better camouflage. Although the visible mutants disappeared, the recessive gene persisted in the population and occasionally reappeared in the homozygous state. Under predation pressure, homozygous mutant mice were swiftly removed from the population.

Another interesting study is the work by Pennycuik et al. (1990), who observed changes in allelic frequencies in populations of house mice associated with both selective and non-selective factors. A twelve-year study of a population carrying recessive alleles affecting coat colour revealed variation in the proportion of homozygous recessive individuals among new recruits. These variations occurred both in the entire population housed in an experimental enclosure and in five subpopulations living in separate shelters. Changes in the frequency of homozygous recessive individuals were preceded by population bottlenecks and migration between shelters. Analysis showed that males of all colour types had similar fitness, while females of one colour type were slightly less fit. The study concluded that temporal changes in recessive allele frequencies were

primarily driven by genetic drift and migration rather than natural selection, with the impact of these processes influenced by the degree of population isolation.

It is interesting to note that in Slovakia has repeatedly observed flavistic individuals of various rodent species within a relatively small geographical area surrounding the village of Trstené pri Hornáde. In 2016, a flavistic black-striped field mouse (*Apodemus agrarius* Pallas, 1771) was recorded near the city of Košice, approximately 20 km from Trstené pri Hornáde (Čanády, 2016). Earlier, in 2004, the first flavistic specimen of *M. spicilegus* was discovered in the village of Kechnec, about 5 km away (Čanády et al., 2008). Additional flavistic individuals of *M. spicilegus* were subsequently observed near the village of Haniska, located within a 10 km radius of Trstené pri Hornáde (Čanády, 2022). Most recently, a small family group consisting of 13 flavistic house mice was found directly in Trstené pri Hornáde. This accumulation of flavistic individuals in multiple rodent species, including both *Mus* and *Apodemus* genera, within such a limited region, suggests a possible underlying pattern. Since flavism is typically caused by mutations in the *Tyr* gene (tyrosinase), which plays a critical role in melanin biosynthesis, the recurrence of this mutation across different species may not be coincidental. Although spontaneous mutations can occur independently in separate populations, the frequency and geographical clustering of these cases raise the question of whether a localised environmental or genetic factor may be contributing to the increased expression of this anomaly.

Several hypotheses might be proposed to explain this phenomenon (see the also above-mentioned citations). One possibility is the existence of a founder effect or localised inbreeding (e.g., Meagher et al., 2000; Mullen & Hoekstra, 2008; Kingsley et al., 2009; Tian et al., 2015; Nakano et al., 2022; and others) within small and partially isolated rodent populations, which could lead to a higher expression of recessive traits, such as flavism. Another explanation could involve environmental pressures or anthropogenic influences in the region, including habitat modifications, food availability, or even low-level exposure to mutagenic substances, which might indirectly promote the persistence or emergence of pigment mutations (e.g., Nachman et al., 2003; Mullen & Hoekstra, 2008; Cerezer et al., 2024; and others). A third, more speculative possibility involves

genetic introgression between related rodent species (e.g., Wada et al., 1999; Kingsley et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2015; Banker et al., 2022; Zakoh et al., 2023) or gene flow between demes (Baker, 1981; Boursot et al., 1993; Dallas et al., 1995; Duvaux et al., 2011; Linnenbrink et al., 2018; Morgan et al., 2022). However, this would require further genetic investigation to confirm. Despite the current lack of genetic data, the repeated detection of flavistic individuals in such a small area strongly indicates that this is not a random occurrence. A more comprehensive genetic and ecological study of rodent populations in the region would be necessary to identify the causes and mechanisms underlying this localised anomaly.

In conclusion, changes in the genetic structure of small mammal populations, which can be phenotypically manifested through pigmentation anomalies (i.e., genetically inherited recessive traits), may serve as indicators of environmental changes. These changes can also signal population bottlenecks and current or past inbreeding. Therefore, these findings are significant not only in terms of colour anomalies (contributing to the overall knowledge of anomalous colouration in *M. musculus*) but also in terms of genetics.

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